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Research Article

**AGROECOLOGICAL TESTING OF SUGAR SORGHUM,
SUDANESE GRASS AND SORGHUM-SUDANESE HYBRIDS IN
THE NATURAL CONDITIONS OF THE NOVGOROD REGION**Elena Shkodina¹, Olga Balun¹, Sergey Kapustin², Alexander Volodin², Andrey Kapustin³¹ Novgorod Scientific Research Institute of Agriculture, Park str. 2, etc. Borkey, Novgorod district, Novgorod region.,173516, Russia,² North Caucasus Federal Agricultural Research Center, Nikonov str. 49, Mikhailovsk, 356241, Russia,³ North Caucasus Federal University, Pushkin str. 1, Stavropol, 355017, Russia.**Abstract:**

In the conditions of the Novgorod region, forage crops from the southern regions, Sudanese grass, sugar sorghum and sorghum-Sudanese hybrids exhibit high adaptive properties. The best time for harvesting these crops for green fodder and hay is the period from entering the pipe (sugar sorghum) to the appearance of inflorescences and for silage is removed in the phase of milky-wax ripeness. When sowing in the third decade of May, one-year introduced crops can be used for green fodder from mid-July to late August, for silage almost to frost. On average for 2016-2018 the highest yield of green mass for silage was obtained from the sorghum-Sudanese hybrids Navigator (58.6 t / ha), Gvardeets (43.0 t / ha), Sudanese grass Zemlyachka (39.7 t / ha), sugar sorghum Larets (40.5 t / ha). The high yield of green mass of the studied crops increases the efficiency of feed production, provides high fees per hectare of protein, exchange energy. In 2018, Sudan grass Zemlyachka and Sputnitsa, sugar sorghum Silosnoe 88 and Galya, and Sorghum-Sudanka hybrid Navigator were distinguished by the output of dry matter from 1 ha (more than 4 tons). The collection of 1 hectare of protein from Sudanese grass Zemlyachka was 639.3 kg, sugar sorghum Galia 662.9 kg, sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Navigator 601.8 kg. Introduction of introductions from the southern regions to the forage production of the Novgorod region contributes to the expansion of the range of crops grown for feed and feed conveyor, strengthening the feed base and balancing feeding rations in order to effectively manage the process of agroecosystems.

Keywords: introduction, adaptation, green mass, silage, Sudanese grass, sugar sorghum, sorghum-Sudanese hybrid.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Production and processing of agricultural products is one of the components in the economy of the Novgorod region. The territory of the region is in the zone of risky farming, so the agrarian industry specializes in the production of meat and dairy products. Livestock accounts for more than 67% of the total agricultural output. The needs of the population of the region in meat products are fully satisfied by their own agricultural producers, and in milk less than 50%.

To expand the production of dairy products, the crop industry of the region should increase the area under feed crops, ensure high productivity of the feed hectare and the quality of the feed produced [1, 2, 3]. In this regard, farmers need new innovative ways of obtaining feed.

Literary sources [4-7] indicate that there are two main ways to increase crop yields with minimal cost. The first way is to use the achievements of domestic breeders who create new varieties with desired feed characteristics. The second way involves the introduction of new high-yielding crops into production, which traditionally have other areas of cultivation and have high adaptive properties. Replacing the range of traditional crops with varieties and hybrids of the new generation allows more fully utilizing the potential productivity of the soil. In the conditions of the Non-chernozem zone of the Russian Federation, the diversity of crops grown is limited and does not allow to completely solve the problems of the forage industry. Innovative solutions to the problem involve the use of genetic polymorphism in agroecosystems due to the presence of a large domestic stock of plant resources [2, 8].

The outlined trends in climate change make it possible to draw attention to crops traditionally grown for feeding purposes in the southern regions of the country [9, 10]. Their introduction to the Novgorod region will help to diversify and improve the diet of animals, relieves periods of tension in feed and pipelines [11, 12]. Agroecological testing of varieties and hybrids under conditions of a short growing season and low soil fertility of the Non-Black Earth Zone is of interest both for breeders and workers of the agricultural sector of the region [13].

The purpose of the research is to assess the ability of southern annual forage crops of the family of bluegrass (Poaceae) to produce stable yields in the created agroecosystems, as well as indicators of the quality of the feed obtained. To identify among the crops and their varieties most adapted to the conditions of the Novgorod region.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The studies were conducted on the experimental field of the Novgorod Scientific Research Institute of Agriculture in the years 2016-2018. The soils of the site are light loamy, sod-podzolic, their acidity varies in the range of pH = 5.1-6.6. The mass fraction of mobile potassium compounds (K₂O) is 10.1-22.9 mg / 100 g of soil, phosphorus compounds (P₂O₅) is 12.0-73.7 mg / 100 g, the mass fraction of organic matter is 2.81-3.57%. Phenological observations, measurements and counts were carried out in accordance with the Guidelines for conducting field experiments with feed crops of the All-Russian Research Institute of Feed named after V. R. Williams [14].

The predecessor in the research was busy steam in a layer of perennial leguminous herbs. Accounting area plots 10 m², four times repeated, placement systematic.

Sowing was carried out manually, in an ordinary way in the third decade of May upon the occurrence of optimal conditions for seed germination (May 20-22). Before sowing, mineral fertilizers were introduced with 60 kg of active substance NPK per 1 ha. During the growing season, manual weeding and loosening of the soil between the rows were carried out.

The object of study was Sudan grass (*Sorghum sudanense*), sugar sorghum (*Sorghum saccharatum*), sorghum-Sudanese hybrids. The Volga region is represented by a collection of varieties of the Federal State Scientific Institution RosSRIA "Rossorgo", Saratov; Sudanese grass variety Spartanka, sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Melody. From FSBRI "Volga Research Institute of Breeding and Seed Production. P. Konstantinov "studied Sudanese grass cultivar Kinelskaya 100.

The FSBSI "North Caucasus Federal Agricultural Research Center" is represented by cultures of Sudanese grass varieties Sputnitsa and Zemlyachka, sorghum-Sudanese hybrids Navigator and Gvardeets, sorghum sugar Galia, Larets, Silosnoe 88.

During the years of research, the weather conditions of the growing season were very diverse. In 2016, there was an excess of precipitation (HTC 1.73) on the background of moderate temperatures, the frost-free period lasted until October 12. The vegetation period of 2017 was determined by extreme weather conditions. In April and the first half of May, the weather was cold with frosts and did not allow field work. The sum of temperatures exceeding 10 °C (1908 °C) was 11% lower than the average multiyear, the onset of phenological phases in plants was delayed by 2-3 weeks, the frost-free period lasted until October

21, the amount of precipitation exceeded the norm 1.7 times, the HTC was 2.67. In 2018, until mid-May, night frosts with low daytime temperatures and water stagnation in the fields were observed. June was cold, with frosts in the first decade, July, August and September warm and sunny. During the growing season there was a lack of precipitation (HTC 0.89), the frost-free period lasted until September 25.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

During the years of research, when sown at the beginning of the third decade of May, single shoots of sorghum crops appear in 10-14 days, by the beginning of June (in 2017 shoots of plants appeared 3 weeks after sowing), mass shoots appeared within 2-3 weeks (in 2018 year the period of shoots lasted almost a month). At the initial stage, the plants developed very slowly, their height during the first month did not exceed 12-35 cm. The period of intensive growth and accumulation of biological mass in plants began from the second decade of July (in 2017 in August), when during the week growth 1.5-2.5 times. Sudan Kinelskaya 100 grass first entered the heading stage at the end of July - beginning of August (except for 2017). At the end of August - September, panicles of sorghum-Sudanese hybrids were thrown away, Sudan grass Zemlyachka, and sugar sorghum Silosnoye 88. In 2017, the development phase was delayed by 3 weeks, so the earing period began at the Sudanese grass Zemlyachka in September. Sorghum, sugar and sorghum-Sudan hybrids were not thrown away.

In 2016, by the end of the growing season, seeds of the Sudanese grass Kinelskaya 100 ripened. Sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Navigator and Sudanese grass Zemlyachka ended the growing season in the seed formation phase. In 2017, the summer was cold and rainy, but the frost-free period lasted until October 21. By the third decade of September, the seeds of Sudanese grass, Kinelskaya 100, had ripened. By the end of the growing season, the remaining varieties of Sudanese grass were in bloom, sugar sorghum and sorghum-Sudanese hybrids completed the vegetation in the tube release phase. In 2018, the seeds of the Sudanese grass Kinelskaya 100 ripened. The sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Navigator finished the growing season in the seed formation stage. The varieties of Sudanese grass Zemlyachka Sputnitsa, Spartanka, sugar sorghum Silosnoye 88 and sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Melody bloomed by the end of the growing season, sugar sorghum Galia in the third decade of September was in the phase of spraying, sorghum-Sudan hybrid Gvardeets and sugar sorghum Larets in the exit phase the tube.

The best time for harvesting sorghum crops for green fodder and hay is the period from going into the tube (sugar sorghum) to sprouting and the appearance of inflorescences; silage is removed into the phase of milky-wax ripeness of panicles. Sugar sorghum can be harvested on a silo before full ripeness. The periods of the onset of ripeness of crops in the conditions of the Novgorod region on green mass, hay and silage in the years of research are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Duration of the period of pruned maturity in the introduced forage crops in the conditions of the Novgorod region

Culture, variety, hybrid	2016 year		2017 year		2018 year	
	on green mass and hay	for silage	on green mass and hay	for silage	on green mass and hay	for silage
Sudan grass						
Kinelskaya 100	20.06-10.07	10.07-15.08	01.08-15.08	18.08-10.09	15.07-30.07	30.07-05.09
Zemlyachka	01.07-25.08	25.08-12.10	01.08-10.09	10.09-20.10	20.07-15.09	15.08-25.09
Spartanka	-	-	01.08-31.08	01.09-20.10	25.07-05.08	05.08-25.09
Sputnitsa	26.06-15.08	15.08-10.09	01.08-10.09	10.09-20.10	15.07-05.08	05.08-25.09
Sugar sorghum						
Silosnoye 88	28.07-25.08	25.08-12.10	01.08-20.09	20.09-20.10	25.07-20.08	20.08-25.09
Galia	30.07-25.08	25.08-12.10	01.08-20.09	20.09-20.10	25.07-31.08	31.08-25.09
Larets	28.07-5.09	5.09-12.10	3.08-20.09	20.09-20.10	25.07-10.09	10.09-25.09
Sorghum Sudanese hybrid						
Navigator	01.07-20.08	20.08-12.10	01.08-20.09	20.09-21.10	25.07-20.08	20.08-25.09
Melody	-	-	01.08-20.09	20.09-20.10	31.07-10.08	10.08-25.09
Gvardeets	05.08-01.09	01.09-12.10	01.08-20.09	20.09-20.10	31.07-30.08	30.08-25.09

The length of the period of mowing ripeness depends on the exactingness of the plants to the growing conditions. So, the Sudanese grass Kinelskaya 100 is less demanding and more precocious. It has a shorter time of ripening for harvesting for green fodder and hay in 10-20 days, for silage - 15-35 days.

Cultures with high heat requirements have a longer period for harvesting for green mass: Sudanese grass Spartanka, Sputnitsa, Zemlyachka, sugar sorghum and sorghum-Sudanese hybrids 20-30 days, and in years with low temperature background up to 40-50 days. When sowing in the third decade of May, one-year-old introduced crops can be used for green fodder and hay from mid-July to late August, in cold years during August. For harvesting silage and haylage culture can be used from mid-August, almost to frost.

In 2016-2018 were observing the dynamics of plant growth. Table 2 shows the data of plant heights and the level of yield of introduced species during the period of harvesting green mass for silage. The lack of heat for cultivated crops is the main limiting factor. Excess or lack of moisture has less impact on growth and yield. In tall varieties of Sudanese grass, sorghum of sugar and sorghum-Sudanese hybrids in 2017, the height of plants during the period of silage harvesting was 88-121 cm. In more favorable 2016 and 2018 years. this indicator in the Sudanese grass variety

Zemlyachka and the Sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Navigator (Zersta 90C x Zemlyachka) exceeded 2 m (201-224 cm). In 2018, large plant heights were obtained from the hybrid sugar sorghum Silosnoye 88 (208 cm) and Larets variety (203 cm). For an average of three years, the most significant plant height was found in the plants of the Sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Navigator (183 cm), the Sudanese grass Zemlyachka (175 cm) and the sugar sorghum of the hybrid Silosnoye 88 (167 cm).

The climatic differences in the years of testing, in addition to the height of the plants, ensured different yields of green mass for silage. In the cold year of 2017, its values were 9.8-17.5 t / ha for Sudanese grass, 20.4-21.3 t / ha for sugar sorghum and 16.2-27.0 for sorghum-Sudanese hybrids. In 2016, the yield of sorghum of a sugar hybrid Navigator was 87.2 t / ha, in 2018 - 64.9 t / ha. In the Sudanese grass Zemlyachka, similar indicators were respectively 58.9 and 42.6 t / ha. On average for 2016-2018 the highest yield of green mass for silage was obtained from the sorghum-Sudanese hybrids Navigator (58.6 t / ha), Gvardeets (43.0 t / ha), Sudanese grass Zemlyachka (39.7 t / ha), sugar sorghum Larets (40, 5 t / ha). The remaining options studied indicator was 4.5 t / ha and more lower.

Table 2: Plant height and yield of green mass during the period of its harvesting for silage

Culture, variety, hybrid	Plant height, cm				Yield of green mass, t / ha			
	2016 year	2017 year	2018 year	average	2016 year	2017 year	2018 year	average
Sudan grass								
Kinelskaya 100	128	88	110	109	42,0	10,8	11,3	21,4
Zemlyachka	201	121	204	175	58,9	17,5	42,6	39,7
Spartanka	-	104	196	-	-	14,3	29,1	-
Sputnitsa	178	101	152	144	54,7	9,8	21,6	28,7
Sugar sorghum								
Silosnoye 88	180	113	208	167	37,3	21,0	47,3	35,2
Galia	124	96	156	125	33,6	21,3	44,8	33,2
Larets	112	92	203	136	35,4	20,4	65,6	40,5
Sorghum Sudanese hybrid								
Navigator	224	118	208	183	87,2	23,8	64,9	58,6
Melody	-	104	153	-	-	16,2	34,1	-
Gvardeets	186	104	143	144	52,1	27,0	49,9	43,0
SSD₀₅ t / ha					2,8	1,9	2,5	

Thus, in the conditions of the Nonchernozem zone, southern sorghum crops exhibit rather high environmental plasticity; they are ways to ensure a good level of green mass yield even under adverse weather conditions. To improve

the efficiency of feed use, one of the determining factors is an objective assessment of their composition and nutritional value for the preparation of high-grade rations in order to obtain high animal productivity. In 2018, a zootechnical analysis of the studied crops and varieties was carried out to determine the content of the main quality indicators (Table 3).

Table 3: The quality of green mass of introduced crops

Culture, variety, hybrid	Yield of green mass, t / ha	Mass fraction of dry matter at natural moisture, %	Dry matter collection, t / ha	Mass fraction in dry matter		Content in 1 kg of dry matter	
				dry matter, %	cellulose, %	exchange energy, MJ	feed units
Sudan grass							
Kinelskaya 100	11,3	18,2	2,1	9,51	33,0	9,1	0,67
Zemlyachka	42,6	11,9	5,1	12,61	28,6	9,9	0,79
Spartanka	29,1	15,4	4,5	10,9	31,8	9,3	0,70
Sputnitsa	21,6	15,5	3,3	6,71	25,8	10,4	0,87
Sugar sorghum							
Silosnoye 88	47,3	14,2	6,7	5,42	28,2	9,9	0,80
Galia	44,8	12,8	5,7	11,56	29,7	9,7	0,76
Larets	29,9	12,6	3,8	7,94	28,6	9,9	0,79
Sorghum Sudanese hybrid							
Navigator	52,8	15,7	8,3	7,26	33,1	9,0	0,66
Melody	34,1	13,3	4,5	11,35	28,6	9,9	0,79
Gvardeets	36,9	10,6	3,9	9,53	30,2	9,6	0,74

The yield of green mass is indicated at the time of sampling for agrochemical analysis. According to the content in the dry matter of raw protein, the national standard is Sudan grass Zemlyachka, sugar Gallia sorghum, sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Melody. According to the content in dry matter of raw protein, Sudanese grass Zemlyachka, sugar sorghum Galia, sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Melody correspond to the State standard. Low nutritional value was found in Sudanese grass Sputnitsa and Kinelskaya 100. The remaining varieties have indicators slightly lower, but close to the State standard.

Sudan grass Zemlyachka and Sputnitsa, sugar sorghum Silosnoye 88 and Galia are distinguished by the output of dry matter from 1 ha (more than 4 tons). The champion is a sorghum-Sudankan hybrid Navigator, which in the phase of going into the tube provided 8.3 t / ha of dry matter. A high collection of dry matter per hectare allows even a high protein content per hectare to be obtained when the crude protein content is below the norm. In Sudan grass, Zemlyachka, collecting protein from 1 hectare is 639.3 kg, sugar sorghum Galia is 662.9 kg, and sorghum-Sudan hybrid Navigator is 601.8 kg.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

When sowing in the third decade of May, one-year-old introduced crops can be used for green fodder and hay from mid-July to late August, for silage harvesting from the end of August almost to frost.

On average for 2016-2018 the highest yield of green mass for silage was obtained from the sorghum-Sudanese hybrids Navigator (58.6 t / ha), Gvardeets (43.0 t / ha), Sudanese grass Zemlyachka (39.7 t / ha), sugar sorghum Larets (40.5 t / ha).

The collection of protein from 1 ha in Sudanese grass Zemlyachka was 639.3 kg, sugar sorghum Galia 662.9 kg, sorghum-Sudanese hybrid Navigator 601.8 kg.

REFERENCES:

1. Kosolapov VM, Shpakov AS, Laretin NA. 2014. Methodological guide on the organization of fodder production in specialized livestock farms for the production of milk and meat in the Non-Chernozem zone of Russia. Moscow: Printing House of the Russian Agricultural Academy.
2. Kosolapov VM, Shamsutdinov ZS, Ivshin GI. 2015. The main types and varieties of forage crops. Results of the scientific activity of the Central Selection Center. Moscow: Nauka.
3. Kapustin S, Volodin A, Kapustin A. Comprehensive assessment of new varieties and hybrids sugar sorghum in the conditions of south Russia. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2019; 06(06): 11512-11517.
4. Kosolapov VM, Kozlov NN, Klimenko NA. Environmental breeding of perennial forage grasses. Fodder Production, 2019; 4: 25-30.

5. Degunova NB, Klokova VV, Danilova YB, Shkodina EP. A Model of Efficient Management of Production Process of the Agro-Ecosystem on the Basis of Minor Forage Crops under the Conditions of Novgorod Oblast'. *Agrarian Russia*, 2016; 2: 27-32.
6. Degunova NB, Danilova YB, Shkodina EP. Prospects for the use of forage crops to create green conveyors in the conditions of the Novgorod region. *Science Almanac*, 2015; 6(8): 169-177.
7. Degunova NB, Danilova YB, Shkodina EP. Opportunities for obtaining high-protein feed in the conditions of the Novgorod region. *Multifunctional adaptive feed production*, 2015; 6(54): 107-115.
8. Kapustin SI, Volodin AB, Kapustin AS, Kravtsov VV, Lebedeva NS. The combinational capacity of the lines and the level of heterosis in the hybrids of grain sorghum. *Research journal of pharmaceutical, biological and chemical sciences*, 2018; 9(4): 1547-1556.
9. Ivanov AL. Global climate change and its impact on agriculture in Russia. *Agriculture*, 2009; 1: 3-5.
10. Kapustin SI, Volodin AB, Kapustin AS. Inheritance of morphological and fertile characters in heterozygous sorghum hybrids. *Ukrainian journal of Ecology*, 2018; 8(3): 239-247.
11. Zhukova MP, Volodin AB, Kapustin SI, Kapustin AS. Comprehensive assessment of new varieties of Sudanese grass and sorghum-Sudanese hybrids. *Bulletin of the Stavropol Research Institute of Agriculture*, 2017; 3(27): 33-37.
12. Kapustin SI, Volodin AB, Kapustin AS, Vlasova OI, Donets IA, Golub AS. The use of sorghum-Sudanese hybrids in the north Caucasus. *Research journal of pharmaceutical, biological and chemical sciences*, 2019; 10(2): 646-653.
13. Shkodina EP, Volodin AB, Kapustin SI, Kapustin AS. 2018. Agro-ecological testing of annual forage crops in the Novgorod region. *Methods and technologies in plant breeding and plant growing*. Kirov: FARC of the Northeast Publishing.
14. Williams VR. 1987. *Guidelines for conducting experiments with fodder crops*. Moscow: All-Russian Research Institute of Feed.